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Title: Understanding the community value from implementing the *Food for Thought* programme in Doncaster: learning and perspectives from key stakeholders.

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Introduction: The Food for Thought programme was a multicomponent health promotion programme within two Doncaster Primary schools in areas of high social deprivation. The programme deployed both growing and cooking workshops over the course of 16-weeks at each school site allowing 'unconventional educators' from the culturally diverse parental community to share knowledge and skills on growing, cooking and traditional cultural cuisine. This study explored perspectives from key stakeholders and parents that experienced the delivery of the programme.

Methods: After ethical approval and recruitment, three semi-structured focus groups with 28 participants were conducted with those who had planned or received the programme's workshops (9 stakeholders and 19 parents). From audio recordings, data were transcribed, anonymised, and analysed for themes (presented in *Italics* in the next section) using a deductive and inductive coding strategy.

Results: The programme provided the *opportunity for skill development* for parents and the flexible and inclusive nature of the workshops left participants *really wanting more*. *Differences on children's participation*, and *issues securing clear expectations* highlighted the need for clearer planning and improved consistency. Parents reported *personal empowerment and achievement*, expressed *pride and enthusiasm of contribution*, and valued the *experiential learning opportunity* for themselves and their children.

Conclusions: Although planning and delivery posed some challenges, the overwhelmingly positive feedback, engaging and aspirational workshop content, and strong demand for continuation highlighted the programme's value. The FfT programme demonstrated considerable potential as a locally embedded approach for encouraging food education, parental involvement and social inclusion in culturally diverse communities in Doncaster.

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